

Economies of Urban Spaces

A Conference within IMC Leeds 2025

— Book of Abstracts —

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Panel I – 148 – Historiographies: 11:15-12:45

148-a – In the shadow of modernization narratives—the historiographical landscape of premodern urban property markets – Lucas Burkart, Universität Basel

The urban factor market (land) in the Middle Ages and the economic practices associated with it have been overshadowed by numerous historiographical traditions and narratives, resulting in a somewhat surprising research vacuum. Although individual studies exist, a systematic analysis of the urban factor market and its significance for the genesis of (proto-)capitalist economic activity is still lacking.

Using examples from Latin Christendom, this paper examines the existing research landscape on the factor market land within the urban economy in the late Middle Ages and early modern period. It discusses established research frameworks and perceived dichotomies such as "city - countryside", "church - state", or "monetary economy - agricultural economy"; such conceptual pairs, however, prove to represent not only inaccurate analytical categories for an adequate understanding of the urban land market, but also actively obscure its role in the historical transformation of pre-modern economic forms with far-reaching implications.

This overview contributes not only to critically reflect on the underlying analytical premises and narratives, but also to help reshape the historiographic framework for future research.

About the Author

Medieval urban history has been one of Burkart's research areas from the time of his dissertation. In changing analytical perspectives (visual, socio-economic, cultural, and more recently digital history) he has published extensively on the history of various cities both north and south of the Alps.

148-b – Merchants' entry into urban and rural real estate: the economic logic of mixed portfolios – Martha C. Howell, Columbia University

Long-distance merchants in late medieval and early modern Europe concentrated their capital in the realm of circulation. Nevertheless, as householders who founded nuclear families and resided in cities, they bought or rented urban properties. Some did more as well, whether as speculators on the urban real estate market or as a landlord class that collected rents from ordinary citizens and institutions alike. Even more commonly, such elite merchants bought landed estates in the surrounding region and often farther afield as well, or they acquired them through marriages to women from landed families.

Scholars have often concluded that such investments reflected merchant's efforts to exit the high-risk mercantile economy and retreat into safer assets. In particular, scholars have emphasized that when merchants bought rural estates, they did so to adopt the lifestyle – and social status – of landed gentry. Using evidence from a rare collection of quasi-autobiographical texts written by long-distance merchants in German-speaking Europe (what the Germans called *Fernhändler*) between about 1400 and 1600, along with material drawn from studies of such merchants elsewhere in northern Europe during this period, I will argue that for the most part merchants' investments in real estate did not signal a retreat from trade or a shift in social aspirations but, instead, an effort to diversify their economic portfolio and secure their wealth. Traders they were, and traders they remained, even as members of the gentry, where in this period they functioned as rentiers, not as agrarian capitalists.

About the Author

Martha Howell, Miriam Champion Emerita Professor of History, specializes in social, economic, legal, and women's history in northern Europe during the late medieval and early modern centuries, concentrating on the Burgundian Netherlands, northern France, and Germany. She is presently working on the culture of credit in northern Europe during the late medieval and early modern centuries. Among her rich list of publications the seminal monograph *Commerce before Capitalism in Europe, 1300-1600* (Cambridge, 2010) is particularly pertinent for the topic of the panels/roundtable on "Economies of Urban Spaces".

148-c – Dealing with a Property Crisis: How Did People Behave in a Medieval Town? – Julie Claustre, Université Paris Cité

Historical studies of housing in medieval Paris have long focused on two aspects. On the one hand, there were the residences of the elite, in other words, the ‘hotels’ that left lasting traces on the topography. Secondly, the allotments of the 12th-13th centuries. In the second half of the 20th century, historians turned their attention to the property market. Paris in the Middle Ages experienced two major real estate crises: one brief and violent, in 1306, and the other long and persistent, in the first decades of the fifteenth century. While the former is well documented in a number of chronicles, the latter is not, although it is mentioned in the ‘Journal du Bourgeois de Paris’. These accounts help us to understand some of the ways in which residents acted in times of property crisis. But other documents need to be consulted if we are to grasp the full extent of the situation. Historical studies carried out in the 1960s and 1970s attempted to understand the fifteenth-century crisis at neighbourhood level by observing transactions in houses archived by certain Parisian landlords. Today, with the advent of new digital research tools and also of new economic history questionnaires, it is possible to sketch out complementary approaches to the real-estate context in 15th-century Paris: at the level of the ordinary inhabitant (thanks to the accounts of a craftsman) and at the level of a powerful landlord (thanks to the e-NDP corpus of cathedral chapter decisions).

About the Author

As full professor of history of the Middle Ages at the Université Paris Cité, Julie Claustre has been working on the history of the economy and society of Paris in the Middle Ages for over twenty years. In particular, she has studied credit and indebtedness through debt collection, the notary's office, and the accounts of a Parisian craftsman. She is currently studying the seigniorship of the Paris cathedral and the seigniorial courts of the Ile-de-France region.

Panel II – 248 – Social Strata and Actors:

14:15-15:45

248-b – Granting Credit and Seizing Land: Monasteries and Other Ecclesiastical Institutions in Basel's Real Estate Economy – Aline Vonwiller, Universität Basel

One thing is certain: the medieval real estate market in Basel was a bustling scene. Properties were bought, sold, and sublet, with married couples acting as important players. Loans were taken out—sometimes jointly with other couples, relatives, or acquaintances—leading to the creation of co-ownerships and the shared use of houses. If debts were not repaid, debtors could resort to court proceedings known as *Frönungen* to settle their obligations and to initiate the seizures of properties.

However, despite the dominance of ecclesiastical institutions in Basel's real estate market, as identified in the HGB dataset, their specific role remains inadequately explored. Ecclesiastical landlords collected levies whenever properties changed hands and extended loans to individuals lacking the financial means to purchase real estate. In doing so, they often bound co-ownerships to themselves via rent agreements.

Quantitative analyses serve as a starting point in this study to explore qualitative questions regarding the role of ecclesiastical institutions in the housing market and their entanglement in medieval society: This paper seeks to explore different ecclesiastical institutions compared in their lending practices: Which ecclesiastical institutions received how much interest over the course of the 15th century? How was their market share spatially distributed across the city? Were there noticeable patterns or differences in how and where loans were granted or interest was collected? Could these patterns be explained by topographic or temporal factors?

Monasteries and collegiate churches also made use of urban court systems for enforcing claims on unpaid debts. But which institutions relied most heavily on court infrastructure? Were there any significant changes in the use of courts during the 15th century? A ranking of the institutions based on their use of court procedures will shed light on their respective roles in Basel's medieval property market.

About the Author

Aline Vonwiller researches urban transactions for her PhD project within the scope of the project *Economies of Space*. With an academic background in history and sociology, she is particularly interested in social interconnections between different social strata and the socio-cultural history of the Middle Ages. Her work combines the subtle qualitative methods developed in historical research over long periods with modern quantitative approaches made possible by current digital methods.

248-c – Bound by Space?: Occupational Clusters, Neighbourliness, and Trust in Late Medieval Bruges – Ward Leloup, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

In medieval and early modern urban societies, sociability and trust are believed to have been shaped by various “binding” contexts, including kinship, (guild) association, and neighbourhood. Only recently have historians empirically substantiated the role of each of these contexts, their relative importance, and changes in their contribution over time. This paper contributes to these debates by investigating the interplay between socio-occupational relations and urban space in late medieval Bruges (Low Countries). Specifically, it examines the locational patterns of craftsmen working in the leather industry between the fourteenth and sixteenth century. This leather industry, fundamental to premodern societies, was controlled in Bruges by the guilds of the tanners, *dobberers*, curriers, and shoemakers. These artisans were bound in socio-occupational networks by guild membership and business relations. This paper addresses the question of whether these socio-economic bonds spatially translate into occupational clusters, as is often assumed by historians and geographers alike. While the sixteenth-century socioeconomic topography can be reconstructed using fiscal records, for the preceding period this research relies on the registers of the Orphan’s Court in Bruges recording orphans’ inheritances, including real estate. The findings reveal differing spatial patterns for the various occupational groups within the leather industry, which can be explained by the varying spatial needs of each group and organizational differences in production. Additionally, the paper explores the extent to which the bonds of trust involved in securing the orphans’ inheritances were informed by a spatial context. This way, it sheds light on the interconnectedness of social, occupational, and spatial networks in a premodern city.

About the Author

Ward Leloup is a member of the Social History of Capitalism (SHOC) Research Group at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel and the Henri Pirenne Institute for Medieval Studies at Ghent University. Apart from being a teaching assistant at the VUB History Department, he is currently preparing a PhD dissertation on economic, social, and spatial relations between artisans in late medieval Bruges (14th-16th century), with a specific focus on craftsmen active in the leather industry.

Panel III – 348 – Digital Methods: 16:30- 18:00

348-a – On the Use of Geomatics for the Analysis of Land Records and the Understanding of Medieval Urban Spatialities – Margot Ferrand, Université d'Avignon

In this presentation, I aim to revisit the methodology implemented during my doctoral research. My research focused on urban spatialities in Avignon between the 13th and 15th centuries, with the primary objective of analyzing the impact of the papacy's installation in the Rhône city on local powers. By studying specific land records, I explored the management of seigneurial landholding, land ownership, and urban practices. We will particularly examine how the city walls transitioned from common property, intended for collective use, to private parceling. The approach taken is multimodal, utilizing maps, graphs, and a geographic information system (GIS) to represent the landholding and social dynamics. In particular, 14th-century terriers were used to analyze property networks and the spatial distribution of seigneurial landholdings. The data modeling work, enriched by a named entity recognition program, allows for a detailed analysis of spatial perceptions at various scales and from different perspectives, ranging from the landowners to the tenants. The quantitative and serial methods employed reveal the social and economic logics underlying the urban configuration of the time, while also highlighting the interactions between the various landholding actors and their strategies for controlling urban land.

About the Author

Margot Ferrand, did her PhD in History and Geomatics and is winner of two prizes for her thesis “Usages et représentations de l'espace urbain médiéval. Approche interdisciplinaire et exploration de données géo-historiques d'Avignon à la fin du Moyen Âge.”

348-b – Who Lives Where in Vienna?: Mapping the Medieval City through the Digitisation of Property Registers – Julian Helmchen, Freie Universität Berlin

In the late Middle Ages, Vienna was one of the most populous cities in the empire, with an estimated 20,000 inhabitants living in 2000 houses. Municipal property registers have been recorded since 1368. Whenever a house changed hands, the type of transaction, the transaction partners and a description of the location of the transferred property were noted. As the concept of a postal address with a fixed house number was yet unknown, the scribes referenced the location of houses by adjacent roads and neighbors.

From the period between 1420 and 1517, there are around 9500 entries with just as many of these location descriptions. Thanks to the digitization of the property registers, it is now possible to decipher the precise location of the houses on the city map. An individual workflow had to be created for this task. First, 3500 handwritten pages had to be transcribed. Then the relevant information had to be filtered out of the entries. Using rule-based approaches, each entry was collated into an index card in which the seller and recipient of a house as well as the adjacent roads and buildings were identified. These were combined semi-automatically to create house biographies and neighborhood chains. The paper will focus on the challenges that arose, how these were dealt with and what further potential the data offers.

About the Author

Julian Helmchen studied History and Classical Archaeology at the Free University of Berlin. He completed his Master's degree in History there in 2018 and a second Master's degree in Archaeology at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin in 2021. From 2021 to 2024, he was a research assistant in the “Mapping Medieval Vienna” research project led by Thomas Ertl at the FU Berlin. As part of this project, he is also writing his dissertation entitled “Who lives where in Vienna? Digitization and analysis of Viennese land registers from 1420 to 1517”. Julian Helmchen is currently a lecturer at the FU Berlin and is working on completing his dissertation.

348-c – Tracing the Old City of Basel: Data Modelling and the Automated Extraction of Events, Actors, and Objects in the Historical Land Records – Ismail Prada Ziegler, Universität Bern

“Vesula Hansen Mitli, des tischmachers sel. Witwe verkauft an den Spital 3 lb jährl. zinses, ab jrem Hus u Hofstatt an den Spalen um 60 lb.”

Transl.: “Versula, widow of Hans Mitli, the tablemaker rip., sells to the hospital 3 lb yearly rent from her house at the Spalen for 60 lb.”

The Historical Land Records comprise over 100 thousand index cards similar to the shortened example provided above. These records describe interactions in the Basel real estate market such as property sales, rent purchases, and legal procedures relating to housing, offering a rich source for social and economic history. Each index card is a copy or summary from a historical source dating between late medieval and early modern times.

To enable large-scale analysis and digital access to the information contained in these texts, we employ a number of artificial-intelligence-driven methods: First, each handwritten text is automatically transcribed using the Transkribus platform. Then, entity recognition techniques identify persons, organizations, properties, dates, monetary values, and more information in the texts. This is done in a layered manner, allowing to annotate broader categories (e.g., persons) as well as finer details (e.g. occupation, family roles). Furthermore, we extract events, such as the sale of a house or the transfer of rent, to understand how these entities relate and interact. We also apply normalization techniques to unify historical variants of terms (e.g., job titles or names of institutions).

We will conclude the presentation with an example of how these methods allow us to ask new historical questions and trace patterns across time and space that would be difficult to uncover manually.

About the Author

Ismail Prada Ziegler studied History and Computational Linguistics at the University of Zurich. During his master's, he started to focus on the adaptation of information extraction techniques for the pre-modern domain. As part of the SNF project *Economies of Space*, he is now writing his dissertation in Digital Humanities at the University of Berne, searching for the best ways to enable large-scale analysis of a corpus like the Historical Land Records.

Panel IV – 448 – Future Perspectives and Next Directions – A Round Table

Discussion: 19:00-20:00

This roundtable belongs to the *Economies of Urban Spaces* series (I - III) and will weave together the three sessions that have preceded it and explore potential future paths that (economic) history will probably be going to take.

As a pillar of feudalism, land ownership and landed property has been a focus of/for medieval research for a long time. To this day, they are strongly associated with rural economies and manorialism; for a long time, the economy of landed property also fuelled the idea of medieval societies as largely static, both socially and economically – a ‘counter-world’, so to speak, to the dynamics of modern societies and especially of modern capitalism!

Against this backdrop, the roundtable plans to discuss how different research perspectives can contribute to integrating the economy of urban spaces into a more encompassing analytical framework, bringing together case studies, digitally driven methods, and the critical reflection about established historiographies of urban history and narratives on the genesis of capitalism.